

On Crimes and Punishments by Cesare Beccaria: A Book Review

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Beccaria was a young, 25 years old, eager to bring reforms in the Italian criminal justice system. His proposed treaties were the first systematically suggested reforms in the criminal justice system. As noted:

“In order that punishment should not be an act of violence perpetrated by one or many upon a private citizen, it is essential that it should be public, speedy, necessary, the minimum possible in the given circumstances, proportionate to the crime, and determined by the law”.

With these above-stated words, Beccaria proposed the *Dei delitti e delle pene*, concise yet elaborated treaties of Italian Enlightenment or classic propositions of the modern Italian Laws. Beccaria was a passionate, brave and loud critique of old criminal laws and considered them as barbaric, brutal, unjust and inhumane against the criminals. He postulated *On Crimes and Punishment* as a reform for the Italian Enlightenment as it was based on legality, the rule of law and lenience towards criminals. Beccaria argued that the purpose of punishment should be reform, not exploitation any sense. He also raised voice again judicial torture as a violation of fundamental individual rights and considered them as a misuse of power, judicial rights and laws. Beccaria emphasized for judicial reforms, the welfare of criminals and efforts to make them better humans through legislation and justice

Beccaria also lashed out the corrupted judges, lawmakers and legal stakeholders. Likewise, he also argued that the penalties should be based only on the several offences and, the alleged criminal should be saved from tyranny as he believed that the success of justice system depends more on certainty rather than the severity of the punishment. The excessive sentence is nothing but injustice, tyranny and violation of one's rights. Treaties proposed by Becca were advantageous and proved as much influential on the Blackstone and Bentham. Nonetheless, it also influenced the utilitarian in the system of penal justice and later for the development of the criminal justice system in the twentieth century.

Even for today's theorists, critics, criminologists and the lawmakers, Beccaria's thoughts on the criminal justice system and propositions regarding the significant amendments proposed by him, are widely acknowledged and provide a primary

baseline to the modern practitioners and law-making bodies as today, the purpose of punishment is common reform and wellbeing.

1. ORIGINS OF BECCARIA'S IDEOLOGICAL PROPOSITIONS:

From 1763 to 1764, the junior philosophers (including Beccaria) started brainstorming and discussing the Italian laws. They criticized the rules and attributed them to the exploitation of human rights and human reform purposes. Beccaria and his friends accused the Italian laws and developed unified thoughts and opinions against the existing laws and practices.

This small circle of critics and young individuals was widely known as “*Academy of fisticuffs*” or “*Accademia dei pugni*”. They made collective arguments, mutual agreements on the brutality and misuse of legislative power against criminals and accused the judiciary as partial, brutal and not aimed towards reformation. However, despite having a mutual agreement, the unification of thoughts, classic criticism ability, this group only lasted for five years (1763 to 1768). Their thoughts and critical thinking also influenced other criminologists and policymakers to rethink about the laws and their purposes. Modern philosophers like Immanuel Kant, Karl Marx and international law-making bodies (UNCHR, UNHR, UN) also acknowledge Beccaria's thoughts as provided a baseline to human rights advocacy in general and prisoners' right in particular.

2. CRITICISM AND APPRAISALS:

Initially, Beccaria's propositions gained not only many appraisals but also, many philosophers also criticized it as against the laws or leniency towards criminals. Many people also considered it as a partial and unjust approach against victims or sufferers. For the classical jurists, treaties presented by Beccaria were threatening for law and order. Nonetheless, *Gazette littéraire de l'Europe* called it as Rousseau's Social Contract or socialism in Italy, attacking the criminal justice system. The author of Italian penal treaties Pierre-François Muyart de Vouglans, also criticize Beccaria's “On Crime and Punishments” and called it the humiliation of human honour, giving peace to the criminals and not providing compensation or relief to the victims of the crimes. Muyart de Vouglans also warned the readers about the intensity of criticism as alarming and potentially harmful for the democracy, integrity of civil rights and highly problematic for the justice system.

However, Beccaria's “On Crime and Punishments” also became a pathway to brainstorm further and theoretical grounds such as Foucault's genealogy of the prison in *Discipline and Punish*, as Foucault's perfectly represented the Beccaria's ideas and criticisms during the eighteenth-century movements.

Over the centuries, Beccaria's On Crimes and Punishments has provided a strong foundation and roots to a classic school of thought regarding law and criminology. For instance, Richard Bellamy's attributed Beccaria's On Crimes and Punishments to positive and negative criticism, a collection of criminology and law-related aspects, a torchbearer of human reformation, classical food for thought especially for the English legislations in general.

Encyclopédie. André Morellet, abbé was also inspired by the Beccaria's treaties and invited many of his colleagues to discuss Beccaria's "On Crime and Punishments", and they experienced reading the first English passage of the essay by translated by Morellet. They all found it inspiring and acknowledge Beccaria's as useful for the existing law-making bodies. Later, significant critics like Muryart de Vouglans also confessed their criticism as a mistake and acknowledged Beccaria's On Crimes and Punishments as a fundamental part of law and criminology.

Beccaria's treaties were later translated in English and utilized by the English lawmakers. Both Blackstone and Bentham were based on the Beccaria's "On Crime and Punishments". Especially Blackstone made arguments under Beccaria's proposition as argued that convictions and penalties should be reformation instead of punitive.

Similarly, Benthem's manuscript entitled "*Rationale for Punishment* was also published in 1775, based on Beccaria's "On Crime and Punishments" and opposing the inhumane imprisonment and violation or misuse of juridical powers.

Thus, both Blackstone and Benthem mutually agreed against the humiliation of people as criminals, misuse of power and prolong imprisonment as unnecessary and highly harmful rather than reformative. They both emphasized on swift punishments, constructive reformation and the role of legislative bodies as positively preventing future crimes.

3. THEORETICAL AMALGAMATION:

A reflection of Beccaria's "On Crime and Punishments" can be considered as a foundation building block of Social Contract Theory. Social Contract Theory asserts that one's political and social responsibility mainly rely on the agreement to reform the society they live in. Here Beccaria's propositions are deeply associated with the Social Contract Theory as Beccaria also attributes legislation and judicial system as political and social committed to working for the wellbeing. As Beccaria's considered the Social Contract of wellbeing and reform between judiciary and society, his propositions are powerfully correlated with the conceptual recommendations of the Social Contract Theory. Here although Verri's and Beccaria's were the same about social wellbeing, the Beccaria's concepts were more direct and robust as he explicitly criticized natural heirachy⁷ and aristocracy in Italian society.

Likewise, Beccaria's criticism of strict punishment was robust yet logical. As he argued that punishment directed towards one's wellbeing and reform is acceptable and ethical. However, beyond the necessary and righteous punishment or excessive chastise is tyranny. Here the argument is, that the sentence should be aimed at harming the crime, to stop the crime and to mitigate the possibility of future crimes. The focus should be minimizing the chances of recidivism instead of harming the person or criminal.

Moreover, Beccaria also proposed the proportionality of crime and punishment. In other words, he believed that a criminal should be punished in a way that if he thinks about re-committing the crime, he may also think about its consequences. For this purpose, Beccaria emphasized to create a closer connection between crime and punishment.

Beccaria further described the potential consequences of having same punishments or at least the exact nature of penalties in worsening the crime. As he argues that if the same sentences would be given to both small and more significant criminals, the legal system will be unjust and exploit the laws. As for the big criminals, the same punishment as for the small crimes, will not be a more significant concern anymore.

Beccaria widely believed in the rule of law and rights of the common man. He emphasized the use of syllogism to provide a strong background for proposing punishments for the crimes. At this moment, syllogism Beccaria means logical reasons, rational decisions justified by legal structure and policymakers.

Beccaria also opposed the death penalty or execution of criminals. Once again, his argumentation could be found in Social Contract Theory, as he described the judicial power and law responsible for welfare and reformation. For Beccaria, the death penalty does not fit well in social wellbeing or mitigating the crimes. Instead, it can be considered only as only harming the person but leaving the crime alive. However, despite Immanuel Kant supported Beccaria's "On Crime and Punishments", he strictly rejected the idea against capital punishment. Although along-with Beccaria opposed one's right to harm himself, he also proposed strict punishment against heinous crimes. Therefore, we found that Beccaria's "On Crime and Punishments" provided the necessary foundation to human rights, criminal justice system and several philosophical ideas. Although Beccaria's essay faced immense criticism, it also offered baseline to many laws designed and imposed, especially in Italy and Western Europe. Here if we mention, civil rights protection by Habeas Corpus, it would be of greater importance. As Habeas Corpus was also about civil rights protection and prison rights protection, focused towards refraining from tyranny against people which is the main focus of Beccaria's "On Crime and Punishments".

4. FIVE MAJOR TYPES OF CRIMINAL LAWS AND PUNISHMENTS:

As mentioned earlier, Beccaria's convictions regarding Italian laws were based on reformation. The idea behind "*Beccaria's on Crime and Punishments*" was aimed at using laws to decrease the inclination towards crimes through punishment. Here Beccaria also believed that punishing brutally or exploitation the criminal cannot only harm their psychological and social lives also, it is a human rights violation and contradictory of objectives of legislation.

The impact of Beccaria's thoughts can be clearly seen on Blackstone, Bentham and origins of Utilitarianism in penal justice system. As we know that Beccaria believed the aim of law is to achieve common wellbeing and justice for all, here the thoughts reflect the primary purpose of law which is "social welfare" and "equality" for all to have a peaceful society. According to Beccaria, although people are naturally inclined to crimes, hostility and anti-social behavior, we can repress this natural instinct and take it into positive direction through laws and punishments. Under Beccaria's convictions, we can propose five major types of criminal law and punishment:

i. Retribution:

Local laws and legislation aims to punish the criminals in some way. Her the objective is not to harm the individual nor is to psychologically exploit them. Instead, the basic aims are to compensate the damage cause by the criminal act by using the "balance the scales." For instance, if a person commits robbery, his punishment should be based on his personal reformation by using reformative punishments such as jailed up with restricted activities including educational courses. However, if someone commits a heinous crime such as murder, punishment does not only aim to reform the person but also to exemplify him for the society by life imprisonment.

ii. Deterrence:

Individual deterrence is focused towards making the criminal avoiding the specific crime. Here the aim is to complete deter the criminal from recidivism that also deter the other members of society to refrain from relevant criminal acts. For instance, imposing heavy fines on violating the traffic rules may also deter the public from infringement of traffic laws. Once a person violates traffic rules and get fine of \$500, other people will also obey the laws to avoid financial loss.

iii. Incapacitation:

Incapacitation keeps the criminals away from society for their welfare. Although, life prison is also based on Incapacitation, in general terms drugs addicts can come under this type of criminal offense. Although, taking drugs is not a crime in many countries, yet when the individual reformation is the goal, Incapacitation is an only way to help the addicts to quit taking drugs.

iv. Rehabilitation:

Usually the aim of rehabilitation is same as social and psychological welfare, here criminals are treated more sophisticatedly to follow the designate rules in prison. Here Incapacitation and rehabilitation sound similar, yet they are different. For example, teenage boy violates traffic rules and does not have driving license, he is sent to rehabilitation center to learn discipline and obligating the basic laws.

v. Restoration:

Restoration is a victim-oriented theory of criminal punishment. The aim is to repair, through state authority, any injury inflicted upon the victim by the offender. For example, one who embezzles will be required to reimburse the amount inappropriately acquired. Restoration is commonly connected with other goals of criminal justice and is closely correlated to notions in civil law, i.e., reversing the sufferer to their primary position before the damage.

Moreover, Beccaria's notions views on the justifications of a legal social order are formulated as follows: "Laws are the circumstances under which individuals, usually autonomous, strengthen themselves in society. Exhausted of existing in a constant position of war, and of relishing the freedom which became of little significance, from the obscurity of its span, they dedicated one part of it, to experience the rest in unity and agreement. The aggregate of all these divisions of the freedom of each individual established the autonomy of a society; and was placed in the hands of the autocrat, as the legal custodian. But it was not adequate only to establish the security; it was also important to support it from the encroachment of each person, who will always attempt to carry away from the public, not only his part but to encroach on that of others."

Thus here the essay concludes with a closing thought that the austerity of penalties ought to be relevant to the nature of the nation itself. Stronger and easily felt consequences have to be made on individuals' only just out of the malignant state. A lightning hit is needed to end a vicious lion who is aggravated by a gunshot. But as people become tempered by society, sensitivity increases. And as it does so, the severity of punishments should diminish, if the association between the object and the impression is to remain steadfast.

5. CONCLUSION:

The current article focused on providing a comprehensive review on the Cesare Beccaria's renowned books entitled "On Crimes and Punishments by Cesare Beccaria". This books indicated the humanitarian approaches adopted by Cesare regarding laws and their purposes. The classical school of thought attributed to Cesare has strong roots in the international laws, and also emphasize on the local laws to follow the main aims behind laws and legislative systems. Cesare not only provides the solutions regarding complex legal systems and laws violating the human rights in general, also discussed the approaches that are considered a s justification to use laws as reformatory approaches.